

Using the AIDET-CT to Enhance Communication in a Private Practice and Improve Patient Satisfaction Scores

Victoria Marroquin, DNP, RN, PHN --- Hannah Fraley, PhD, RN, CNE, CPH --- Kristina Fortes, DNP, RN, FNP-BC, ACHPN

Background

- Patient experience can be impacted by low patient satisfaction and poor communication among providers, staff, and patients.
- Small private practice settings with low patient satisfaction can be impacted financially and struggle to retain patients.
- A small private practice in East LA identified ongoing low patient satisfaction scores and negative Yelp reviews on the internet as an area for improvement.

Purpose

Using the PDSA framework, the purpose of this QI project was to implement and evaluate the evidence-based standardized Communication Tool AIDET-CT to address low patient satisfaction scores and internet Yelp reviews/comments and enhance communication skills between staff and patients and to improve the overall patient care experience at the site.

Methods

Design: A QI project guided by the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) Model

Setting: A Private Practice in East Los Angeles, CA that serves about 600 patients monthly

Sample: Health Care Providers (5), Medical Assistants (4), Front Desk Clerks (2), Office Manager, and the Information and Technology member

Outcome Measure:

- Patient Satisfaction Score
- Number of completed AIDET-CT checklists per group
- Number of completed AIDET-CT checklists per team member

Framework: PDSA Model for Quality Improvement

ACT

- Review findings from the implementation of the AIDET-CT checklist
- Discuss findings with the project team
- If satisfied with the outcome, continue the process, if not start a new PDSA cycle

STUDY

- Evaluate effectiveness of the AIDET-CT checklist
- Identify barriers to implementation of the intervention
- Collect feedback from staff members
- Measure the process after gathering data

PLAN

- Assess the issues
- Review the communication flow in the PP
- Review literature
- Identify team members' roles
- Develop a plan of implementation
- Involve the team members in the plan (who, what, where and when)

DO

- Educate the stakeholders on current issue being addressed
- Implement the proposed intervention
- Plan ongoing meetings
- Educate team members
- Gather data weekly

Results

References

Discussion

Despite limited data collected, the QI project highlighted areas of improvement:

- The need to tailor the AIDET-CT checklist to meet the demands of the PP
- The need for a Staff Educator
- The need for regular staff meetings
- The need for full access to patient satisfaction survey data

Limitations

Several Limitations were faced during the implementation stage of this QI project:

- Limited number of HCPs, time commitment at PP decreased due to hospital rounding
- Small sample
- Short project duration
- Small private practice
- Limited data available for comparison
- COVID-19 Restrictions and mandates

Clinical Implications

Future recommendations for practice include:

- Integrating the AIDET-CT checklist into the Electronic Health Record
- Tailoring the components of the AIDET-CT checklist to the specific needs of the PP
- The AIDET-CT checklist should be implemented with all the patients of the PP

Conclusions

- The AIDET-CT was implemented and evaluated using the PDSA Model
- There was a notable increase in patient satisfaction scores from 89% to 98%.
- Team communication was enhanced through the PDSA team approach
- No new Yelp reviews/comments were noted post-implementation of AIDET-CT